

THE IMPORTANCE OF PRONUNCIATION IN LEARNING ENGLISH AS A SECOND OR FOREIGN LANGUAGE. LITERATURE REVIEW

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Abstract: Learning a second or foreign language is not easy as the culture, the usage of articulatory organs, accent and the letters on the alphabet are various and can cause serious misunderstandings and complexity of the pronunciation of English. Because of the differences in the pronunciation the way of communication with different countries causes the misunderstandings in the language. However, the teachers try to give correct english pronunciation instructions and allocate time for practicing the pronunciation with students, there are many problems in this are of study. This article aims, to find out the problems of pronunciation rules and utter the significance of pronunciation in learning any language as a second or foreign language in the case of english language, as english is widely learnt language throughout the world.

Keywords: English language, pronunciation, significance of pronunciation, teaching pronunciation instructions.

ВАЖНОСТЬ ПРОИЗНОШЕНИЯ ПРИ ИЗУЧЕНИИ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА КАК ВТОРОГО ИЛИ ИНОСТРАННОГО. ЛИТЕРАТУРНЫЙ ОБЗОР

Аннотация: Выучить второй или иностранный язык непросто, так как культура, использование органов артикуляции, акцент и буквы в алфавите различны и могут вызвать серьезные недоразумения и сложность произношения английского языка. Из-за различий в произношении способ общения с разными странами вызывает непонимание в языке. Тем не менее, преподаватели стараются давать инструкции по правильному английскому произношению и выделяют время для отработки произношения со студентами, в этой области обучения возникает много проблем. Эта статья направлена на то, чтобы выяснить проблемы правил произношения и выразить значение произношения при изучении любого языка как второго или иностранного в случае английского языка, поскольку английский язык широко изучают во всем мире.

Ключевые слова: английский язык, произношение, значение произношения, обучение произношению.

INTRODUCTION

English is the language that become the world language the language of many countries and almost all technologies, instructions and the developed governments language. So, learning English is important nowadays. While learning students pay more attention on the grammar, lexicology, and vocabulary of the language, but the pronunciation and phonological knowledge of this language stayed as the least learnt matter. However, the pronunciation plays a vital role in communicative processes.

To learn the correct pronunciation firstly we must find out what is the pronunciation is, and the place of it in the teaching and learning methods. While, knowing the significance of pronunciation we stay encouraged to learn the new lexica with proper pronunciation. For instance, the minimal pairs ‘think’ and ‘sink’ are the example of the pronunciation, the first sounds of each words are similar but the pronunciation is various and if we mispronounce one word, we change the meaning of the sentence that we are speaking. Similarly, all words are similar in the

pronunciation and however the letter in English alphabet only 26 letters, there are 44 individual sounds (20 vowel sounds and 24 consonant sounds).

The main reason of not teaching the proper pronunciation instructions to our students is continuing to be the lack of time in teaching. We must pay more attention in this area of study and teach the pronunciation instructions more to provide the correct speaking and communicative disciplines. We learn the language mostly in communicative purposes and learning pronunciation is important skills to acquire.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The definition of pronunciation.

Pronunciation is described as the act of pronouncing sounds according to the MERRIAM WEBSTER dictionary[1] and similarly Macmillan dictionary also defines it as the way in which a word or language is pronounced or the ways that somebody speaks another foreign language [2]. The definition of pronunciation given by scholars Gilakjani pronunciation is the act of producing understandable sounds to convey for a communicative purpose. In brief, pronunciation is the pronouncing the sounds. By pronouncing we start to communicate with other, express our feelings, emotions, ideas and opinions, this way is the ordinary way of conversating with others. While communicating in foreign language we must pronounce correctly the sounds of that language to make our speech and words understandable for them. As we seen the example before in the case of minimal pairs if the change even one sounds the meaning of the word is changed.

The significance of pronunciation.

English pronunciation is taught inattentively and underestimated by many students. However, everyone speaks the language in the various ways of pronunciation of words. The significance of pronunciation is obvious to everyone, but still the needed attention is no paid enough to this area of teaching because of the lack time according to teachers stated in [3] 62 out of 100 teachers complained about the lack of time in English classes to teach the proper pronunciation instructions.

The primary goal of learning a second language, in accordance with the Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) philosophy, is simply to increase "communicative competence mastered. In India, the majority of the 125 million English speakers English is taught to students as a second language either in school or when they are in college. It is the first language of the tiny but significant (more than 200 thousand) Anglo-Indian community. Indians pronounce English differently depending on their geography, method of schooling, mother language, etc. Examples include Hindi English, Tamil English, etc. Due to higher education and English-medium instruction, this pronunciation difference has been significantly diminished. [4] Furthermore, without specialised pronunciation instruction, ESL students may experience the negative effects of incorrect English pronunciation. For instance, ESL students' loud non-native accents and the incorrect pronunciation of some vowels and consonants can result in unfavourable social encounters that include workplace harassment and discrimination. Because of this, ESL students frequently prioritise pronunciation in their language learning. However, after spending years studying and acquiring the language, many ESL students still have trouble pronouncing words correctly. One possible explanation for why some teachers might not place a high priority on pronunciation in their course curriculum is that they could believe phonology is not a fundamental aspect of language instruction. Another reason pronunciation instruction is sometimes overlooked is because of how some teachers feel of insufficiency. Due to their own lack of professional pronunciation training, several ESL instructors claim they do not feel competent to teach

pronunciation[5]. A, e, I, o, and u are the five vowels that were taught to us. However, English does have up to twenty different vowel sounds. Eight of these twenty vowel sounds are diphthongal glides, while twelve are pure vowels. That implies that out eight of these twenty vowel sounds are diphthongs, which are a mixture of two vowel sounds. A consonant is a speaking sound that is produced when the vocal tract is completely or partially closed. Furthermore, We need to be aware of the proper word stress placement for the transcription of the words. Because English is an accent-based language, not all syllables are spoken with equal stress throughout a word. For instance, the term "ability" is the predominant sound heard is bi, not "a." If you were to look up this term in a dictionary, you could see something like /bɪlɪ/. Word stress is indicated by the little "" symbol that appears after the letter "a" and before the vowel I (/bɪlɪ/). The pronunciation of a word is now altered by the stress. The matching vowel sound and, as a result, the pronunciation entirely alter as the stress shifts. When we hear someone talk, we notice that they do not speak continuously on the same pitch. The person's voice has many peaks and valleys. The term "intonation" refers to this change in vocal pitch patterns. When conversing, Pronouns, articles, verbs, prepositions, and conjunctions – which are referred to in English as functional words – should be skipped over in favour of the more significant nouns, main verbs, adjectives, and adverbs, which are referred to as content words. In general, there are four main categories of intonation:

1. Peaking (increasing pitch followed by a decrease)
2. Dipping intonation (falls and then rises)
3. Upward intonation,
4. Dropping intonation [6]

Additionally, segmentals, suprasegmentals, sentence stress, rhythm and others are the main knowledge that must be learnt by students.

CONCLUSION.

To sum up, the pronunciation is the important sub-skills to learn during the learning process of Uzbekistan and the main reasons of why teachers do not teach the pronunciation firstly, the awareness of pronunciation instruction they prefer not teaching as it is the least thing to learn, secondly, enough qualification and knowledge of teachers.

REFERENCES.

- [1] <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/pronunciation>
- [2] <https://www.macmillandictionary.com/dictionary/british/pronunciation>
- [3] Quoc, T.X., Thanh, V.Q., Dang, T.D.M., Mai, N.D.N., & Nguyen, P.N.K. (2021). Teachers' perspectives and Practices in Teaching English Pronunciation at Menglish Center. *International Journal of TESOL & Education*, 1(2), pp. 158-175. EOI:<http://eoi.citefactor.org/10.11250/ijte.01.02.009>.
- [4] Priya, M. L. S., & NS, P. K. (2020). Teaching phonetics to enhance pronunciation in an ESL classroom. *Journal of critical reviews*, 7(2), 669-672.
- [5] Cox, J. L., Henrichsen, L. E., Tanner, M. W., & McMurry, B. L. (2019). The Needs Analysis, Design, Development, and Evaluation of the "English Pronunciation Guide: An ESL Teachers' Guide to Pronunciation Teaching Using Online Resources". *TESL-EJ*, 22(4), n4.
- [6] Kobilova, N. R. (2022). Importance of pronunciation in english language communication. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 3(6), 592-597.